

INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Scopus || Electronic journal specializing in Scopus

ISSUE 5

 Acceptance of papers **May, 2026**

**Acceptance of
papers**

Published monthly

Topics

economics,
technology, social
sciences

ISSN 3060-5229

Digital
Object
Identifier

Visit the website
t.me/scopus_IST2100

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Makhmudov Nosir Makhmudovich
DSc., Prof., Academician

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli – Senior
lecturer at TSUI

THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR ELECTRONIC
JOURNAL **"INNOVATION SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY"** HAS BEEN REGISTERED
UNDER THE NUMBER **C-5669633** BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND MASS
COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA) OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE
FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

CONTACTS

Phone: **+998 50 737 87 88**

Website: <https://ist-journal.uz>

Email: innovationist2025@gmail.com

The scientific electronic journal "Innovation Science and Technology" has been included in the list of scientific publications recommended for the publication of main scientific results of dissertations for the award of PhD and DSc degrees in economics and technical sciences, in accordance with the Resolution No. 370 of the Presidium of the Higher Attestation Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated May 8, 2025.

Editorial board:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich,
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of
Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Cham Tat Huei,
Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)

Muhammad Imran Sadiq
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Professor,
Malaysia

Ahmed Aziz Ismail
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc),
Professor (Egypt)

Lee Chin
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), (Malaysia)

Asongu SImplice
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Cameroon

Rui Dang
Doctor of Chemistry (DSc), Professor, China

Zahoor Ahmed
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Turkey

Shujaat Abbas
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Russia

Tina A Coffelt
Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Sciences (PhD),
USA

Abdikarimova Dinara Rustamxanovna
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Kurbonbekova Mohichehra Turobjonovna
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Alimardonov Ilkhom Muzrabshokovich
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Razakova Barno Sayfiyevna
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD)

Khasanov Sarvar Ulugbek ugli
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD)

Kholikova Rukhsora Sanjarovna
Associate Professor (PhD)

CONTENTS

MECHANISMS FOR FORMING AND IMPLEMENTING INVESTMENT POLICY OF COMMERCIAL BANKS... 8 Abduvaliyev Sanjar Abdurahmanovich	8
EVALUATION OF MANAGEMENT EFFICIENCY BASED ON BUDGETING IN ENERGY ENTERPRISES (A FACTOR ANALYSIS CASE OF "HUDUDGAZTA'MINOT" JSC)..... 17 Sobirov Shoyadbek Kurbonaliyevich	17
PORTFOLIO OF POSTAL SERVICES AND THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF ITS DIGITALIZATION23 Mamatkulov Gulom Rustamovich	23
OPTIMIZING THE BALANCE BETWEEN LIQUIDITY AND CREDIT RISKS IN ENSURING BANKING STABILITY 30 Anvarov Asliddin Nabijon ugli	30
ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF RENEWABLE ENERGY DEPLOYMENT IN UZBEKISTAN.....34 Hamroyeva Sabina Ismoil qizi, Dilshod Anvarjonovich Ismailov	34
MODERN TRENDS AND EFFICIENCY OF LENDING TO AGRICULTURAL PRODUCERS IN UZBEKISTAN..39 Shamshetova Gulraushan Sarsenovna	39
ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN YOUTH EMPLOYMENT AND CRIME (CASE OF UZBEKISTAN) 42 Khusniddinova Gulnoza	42
PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE INFRASTRUCTURE OF UZBEKISTAN'S FINANCIAL SYSTEM 47 Qobilova Nodira Qayumjon qizi, Normurodov Kh.E.	47
FOREIGN EXPERIENCE OF INCREASING THE EXPORT CAPACITY OF THE REGION AND SPECIFIC FEATURES OF ITS APPLICATION IN UZBEKISTAN 52 Mamadzhanova Tuygunoy Akhmadzhanovna	52
INSTITUTIONAL APPROACH TO WASTE MANAGEMENT AND ITS ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY 56 Otbosarov Abrorbek Adhamjon o'g'li	56
LOSS MANAGEMENT MATRIX (LOSS MANAGEMENT MATRIX) MODEL IN POWER GRID ENTERPRISES.. 61 Khojimurodov Zukhriddin Shukurullo oglu	61
MICROPROJECTS AS A MEANS OF INCREASING THE FINANCIAL ACTIVITY AND LITERACY OF THE POPULATION 67 Irgashev Anvar Farxodovich	67
INSTITUTIONAL VA TEXNOLOGIK O'ZGARISHLAR SHAROITIDA INNOVATION BANK XIZMATLARINI JORIY ETISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH..... 74 Azlarova Aziza Axrorovna	74
PROBLEMS OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF REGIONAL CLUSTERS IN THE LIGHT INDUSTRY OF UZBEKISTAN 80 Umarkulov Kodirjon Maxamadaminovich	80
DIGITAL FINANCIAL INCLUSION AS A DRIVER OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: EVIDENCE FROM GLOBAL TRENDS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR EMERGING ECONOMIES..... 84 Sabitov Oybek Abduganievich, Sattoriy Fayzullokh Abdijabbor ugli	84
PROPERTIES OF HEAVY CONCRETE DISPERSEDLY REINFORCED WITH NON-METALLIC FIBERS AND SPECIFIC FEATURES OF CALCULATING CONCRETE STRUCTURES BASED ON THEM 90 Usmonova Durdona, Gulomova Dilnura	90
THE EFFECT OF STABLE AND DYNAMIC PRICING ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOR 98 Anvar DEBERDIYEV	98
ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES.. 102 M.O. Yo'ldoshova	102

PEDAGOGICAL EFFECTIVENESS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING POLITICAL SCIENCE AT HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	106
Rasulev Bobirjon Atkhamovich	
IMPROVING THE ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISM FOR REGULATING NON-STANDARD EMPLOYMENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESSES	110
Fayzullayev Nurulla Bakhromovich	
PRIORITIES FOR IMPROVING THE HEALTHCARE FINANCING SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN	117
Gulira'no Atabekovna Ruzmetova	
FACTORS AFFECTING TAX PAYMENT SYSTEMS, EXISTING PROBLEMS, AND THEIR CAUSES	124
Tangirqulov Gulom Baxtiyorovich	
EFFECTIVENESS OF ENVIRONMENTAL TAXES IN REDUCING CARBON EMISSIONS IN UZBEKISTAN: AN ECONOMETRIC APPROACH.....	129
Kuziboev Bekhzod Hamidovich	
WAYS TO DEVELOP QUALITY MANAGEMENT IN THE SILK INDUSTRY OF UZBEKISTAN'S ECONOMY	134
Bahriddinov Asror Rakhmatovich, Boltaev Nazarbek Narzullaevich	
STATE OF LENDING TO SMALL BUSINESS PROJECTS IN COMMERCIAL BANKS AND ITS ECONOMIC-STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.....	138
Nargiza Norqobilova Abdiqodirovna	
CONCEPTUAL DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE MECHANISMS OF ENSURING FINANCIAL STABILITY IN ENTERPRISES.....	143
Asomidinova Mohigulbonu Oybek kizi	
ORGANIZATION OF MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING IN NON-STATE HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS .	148
Xojiboyev Muxiddin Shodimuxamedovich	
THE NATURE AND ESSENCE OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION PROCESSES IN MASS MEDIA ORGANIZATIONS.....	151
Sharipova Shahlo Istamovna	
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS AND EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF ALGORITHMS FOR RECOVERING MISSING (NAN) VALUES IN INFORMATION SYSTEM DATA	156
Yarmatov Sherzodjon Shokir oglu, Orifov Oxunjon Fazliddinzoda	
ANALYSIS OF THE STATE OF MARKETING MANAGEMENT IN MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES	167
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
IMPROVING LOAN PORTFOLIO QUALITY AND CREDIT RISK MANAGEMENT MECHANISMS	173
Turgunov Nodirbek Muminjanovich	
INNOVATION CAPABILITIES AND EXPORT PERFORMANCE: THE MEDIATING ROLES OF SUPPLY CHAIN INNOVATION AND ENTREPRENEURIAL ORIENTATION — EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	177
Mukhammadyaminova Shakhzoda	
URBAN PLANNING OF TRANSPORT INTERCHANGE HUBS NEAR TUBERCULOSIS CARE FACILITIES IN UZBEKISTAN	183
Gabibova Irina Vagifovna, Abdumuminova Diyora Gayratovna	
ADAPTING INTERNAL AUDIT STANDARDS IN BUDGET ORGANIZATIONS TO PUBLIC PROCUREMENT PRACTICES.....	192
Meliboyev Askar Eshmuratovich	
ECONOMETRIC EVALUATION OF INVESTMENT EFFICIENCY IN KHOREZM REGION	197
Otajanov Umid Abdullayevich	
SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF MODERN RECLAMATION AND GIS TECHNOLOGIES ON SALINE SOILS IN KARAKALPAKSTAN.....	205
Tajibaev Berdakh	
ISSUES REGARDING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE “TOLLING OPERATIONS” MODULE IN THE GOODS MOVEMENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM UNDER THE CUSTOMS TERRITORY PROCESSING REGIME	212
Lutpullaev Shukrullo Kudratullaevich	

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL MARKETING IN ENHANCING TOURISM-RELATED BUSINESSES IN UZBEKISTAN

Akmaljon Odilov

Lecturer,

Silk Road International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage

E-mail: akmaljon.odilov@univ-silkroad.uz

Phone: +998 99 600 99 09

Abstract. The paper examines the potential of digital marketing as an instrument for improving the economic development of tourism-related businesses in Uzbekistan. With the rapid digitalisation of the economy, more and more tourism companies are switching from conventional marketing approaches to innovative technologies in order to remain competitive in the global environment. Various digital marketing instruments are studied in this context, such as social media, SEO techniques, influencer marketing, and content personalisation. A quantitative research methodology was used in the current study; thus, data were gathered through a questionnaire administered to a random sample of tourists who had visited Uzbekistan. It has been found that a significant share of tourists uses digital channels intensively to search for tourism-related services while making decisions about their destination. In addition, social networks and influencers play a considerable role in shaping tourists' behaviour and preferences.

Keywords: tourism, marketing, business, economic development, techniques, social media.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola O'zbekistonda turizm bilan bog'liq biznesning iqtisodiy rivojlanishini yaxshilash vositasi sifatida raqamli marketingning salohiyatini o'rganishga qaratilgan. Iqtisodiyotning tez raqamlashtirilishi bilan tobora ko'proq sayyohlik kompaniyalari an'anaviy marketing yondashuvlaridan global muhitda raqobatbardosh bo'lib qolishga imkon beradigan innovatsion texnologiyalarga o'tishni boshlamoqda. Bu borada ijtimoiy mediadan foydalanish, SEO texnikalari, influencer marketingi, kontentni shaxsiylashtirish kabi turli xil raqamli marketing vositalari o'rganilmoqda. Ushbu tadqiqotda miqdoriy tadqiqot metodologiyasi qo'llanildi; shuning uchun ma'lumotlar O'zbekistonga tashrif buyurgan sayyohlarning tasodifiy namunalari orasida so'rovnomma o'tkazish orqali to'plandi. Aniqlanishicha, sayyohlarning katta qismi manzil haqida qaror qabul qilishda turizm bilan bog'liq xizmatlarni izlash uchun raqamli kanallardan intensiv foydalanadi. Bundan tashqari, sayyohlarning xulq-atvori va afzalliklarini shakllantirishda ijtimoiy tarmoqlar va influencerlar muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: turizm, marketing, biznes, iqtisodiy rivojlanish, texnikalar, ijtimoiy media.

Аннотация. В данной работе рассматривается потенциал цифрового маркетинга как инструмента улучшения экономического развития предприятий, связанных с туризмом в Узбекистане. В условиях стремительной цифровизации экономики всё больше туристических компаний начинают переходить от традиционных подходов к маркетингу к инновационным технологиям, которые позволяют им оставаться конкурентоспособными в глобальной среде. В этом контексте изучаются различные инструменты цифрового маркетинга, такие как использование социальных сетей, методы SEO, инфлюенс-маркетинг и персонализация контента. В данном исследовании используется количественная методология; данные были собраны путём проведения анкетирования среди случайной выборки туристов, посетивших Узбекистан. Было установлено, что значительная часть туристов активно использует цифровые каналы для поиска туристических услуг при принятии решений о выборе места отдыха. Кроме того, значительную роль в формировании поведения и предпочтений туристов играют социальные сети и инфлюенсеры.

Ключевые слова: туризм, маркетинг, бизнес, экономическое развитие, методы, социальные сети.

INTRODUCTION

Tourism is one of the most dynamic industries globally and plays a significant role in promoting economic development in many countries. In the era of rapid digital transformation, businesses operating in the tourism sector are increasingly required to modify their traditional marketing approaches in order to effectively utilise

digital channels and attract target audiences. Digital marketing offers tourism-related businesses a wide range of innovative tools and strategies that enhance visibility, strengthen customer engagement, and improve competitiveness in the global market. Furthermore, effective digital marketing practices contribute to increasing customer satisfaction and fostering long-term customer loyalty [1].

LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review provides an overview of existing studies and evidence regarding the functionality of digital marketing in the tourism industry, as well as the relevant themes, key research questions, and emerging trends that shape this field of research. This section explores the intersection between digital technologies and tourism, emphasising the importance of social media, search engine optimisation (SEO), and big data-driven personalisation in influencing consumer behaviour, destination branding, and revenue generation.

The tourism industry increasingly relies on effective and customer-oriented marketing strategies to attract visitors, which has accelerated investments in digital marketing technologies. Contemporary consumer behaviour has changed significantly; therefore, modern business strategies must incorporate digital marketing tools and approaches. Digital marketing platforms facilitate the development of affordable, scalable, and data-driven strategies that effectively address the specific needs of the tourism industry [4].

Social media platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, and YouTube have become integral components of modern tourism marketing strategies. These platforms provide tourism-related businesses with opportunities to reach global audiences through visually appealing and interactive content [3]. Social media also functions as a digital word-of-mouth mechanism that significantly influences tourists during the decision-making process [6]. User-generated content (UGC), including reviews, photographs, and videos shared by tourists, enhances trust in destinations and strengthens perceptions of authenticity [5].

Furthermore, targeted advertising based on users' location, preferences, and behaviour is widely implemented through platforms such as Facebook and Instagram. During the COVID-19 pandemic, social media played a crucial role in maintaining customer engagement, as tourism businesses shared virtual experiences and information regarding safety measures [6]. Consequently, social media has become an effective instrument for tourism companies to strengthen consumer trust and promote travel-related products and services.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research provides a clear explanation of the methodology employed in the study. It includes the research design, data collection procedures, sampling techniques, methods of data analysis, ethical considerations, and the limitations encountered during the research process.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The use of online platforms has become increasingly important in the tourism sector. According to the survey results, 34.6% of respondents stated that they often use online platforms to search for travel-related services, while 23.1% reported using them occasionally. These findings clearly demonstrate the growing dependence on digital channels in tourism-related decision-making processes.

As an increasing number of tourists plan their trips online, maintaining a strong digital presence has become essential for businesses operating in the tourism industry. The results indicate that tourism-related enterprises should prioritise digital transformation and strengthen their online marketing strategies in order to remain competitive and effectively reach potential customers (Table 1).

Table 1

Frequency of using online platforms to search for travel-related services or destinations.

Frequency	Number of Respondents	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Always	8	30.8	30.8	30.8
Never	1	3.8	3.8	34.6
Occasionally	6	23.1	23.1	57.7
Often	9	34.6	34.6	92.3
Rarely	2	7.7	7.7	100.0
Total	26	100.0	100.0	—

This figure illustrates how frequently respondents use online platforms to search for travel-related services.

Categories such as “Always,” “Often,” “Occasionally,” “Rarely,” and “Never” demonstrate variations in the level of digital platform usage in tourism planning activities.

The findings reveal that 34.6% of respondents frequently used online platforms, while 30.8% reported always using them for tourism-related searches. In contrast, only a small proportion of respondents indicated that they rarely or never used such platforms. These results emphasise the growing importance of digital interfaces in influencing tourism-related decision-making processes (Figure 1).

7. How often do you use online platforms to search for travel-related services or destinations?

Figure 1. The role of influencers and social media in shaping travellers' choices (own elaboration).

This diagram illustrates the important role of influencers and social media in shaping travellers' choices. Different levels of influence are represented on a scale ranging from “Not at all” to “Significantly.” The findings indicate that approximately 50% of respondents acknowledged that influencers positively contribute to their travel-related decisions, with Instagram and YouTube identified as the most effective platforms for engagement. These results highlight the growing opportunities for tourism-related businesses to utilise innovative digital marketing strategies in order to strengthen consumer trust, enhance customer engagement, and build long-term relationships with potential travellers.

Furthermore, 96% of respondents stated that personalised content on travel websites significantly influenced their booking decisions. This finding highlights the importance of personalisation in enhancing consumer engagement and satisfaction. Tailored marketing campaigns that address individual preferences and needs are likely to increase conversion rates and strengthen long-term customer loyalty. Therefore, data-driven marketing strategies play a crucial role in building trustworthy and sustainable relationships with customers.

Influencer marketing has become one of the most effective promotional tools within the tourism industry. Approximately 50% of respondents agreed that influencers affect their travel choices. Among social media platforms, Instagram and YouTube were most frequently identified as major sources of travel inspiration. Consequently, tourism-related businesses can benefit significantly from collaborations with influencers to enhance brand awareness and increase market visibility. Since many potential travellers perceive influencer recommendations as relatable and trustworthy, such collaborations may contribute to higher booking rates and increased user engagement.

The survey findings also reveal two major factors influencing tourism-related decisions: visual content and customer reviews. Approximately 54% of respondents indicated that high-quality images and videos strongly influence their travel decisions, while 23% highlighted the importance of ratings and customer feedback. These findings demonstrate that tourism businesses should place greater emphasis on producing visually appealing and professional digital content while encouraging satisfied customers to share positive experiences online. The combination of engaging visual materials and favourable reviews can significantly increase the confidence of potential tourists and positively influence their purchasing decisions.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Digital marketing has become an essential component for modern tourism enterprises seeking to reach broader audiences, enhance customer engagement, and support sustainable business growth. The findings of this study demonstrate that a well-developed digital marketing strategy can significantly improve business visibility, strengthen customer experience, and contribute to increased profitability. At the same time, the research underlines the importance of continuously adapting to developments within the digital environment. The emergence of new technologies, evolving consumer preferences, and changing digital trends create valuable opportunities for tourism-related businesses to become more flexible, innovative, and competitive. Furthermore, effective resource management, data security, and the integration of emerging technologies are important factors that can support long-term success in the digital era.

Based on the findings of the study, several strategic recommendations have been proposed to further improve digital marketing practices in tourism-related businesses. These recommendations highlight the importance of strengthening competitiveness within an increasingly digitalised business environment. In particular, tourism enterprises, especially small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), are encouraged to invest in specialised digital marketing training programmes. Expanding practical knowledge and professional experience in digital marketing implementation may help businesses utilise digital opportunities more effectively. Therefore, training initiatives should focus on practical and industry-oriented learning approaches that provide participants with up-to-date knowledge and hands-on experience related to current digital marketing practices. Moreover, training programmes should include components related to analytics and data analysis, enabling businesses to monitor performance indicators and continuously improve their marketing strategies. By developing these essential digital competencies, tourism enterprises will be better positioned to strengthen their online presence, promote their services more effectively, and utilise digital platforms to attract and retain potential tourists.

REFERENCES

1. Buhalis, D., & Amaranggana, A. (2015). Smart tourism destinations: Enhancing tourism experiences through personalisation. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technology*, 6(1), 37–54.
2. Chaffey, D., & Ellis-Chadwick, F. (2019). *Digital Marketing: Strategy, Implementation, and Practice* (7th ed.). Pearson.
3. Gretzel, U., Sigala, M., Xiang, Z., & Koo, C. (2020). Smart tourism: Foundations and developments. *Electronic Markets*, 30(1), 7–11. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12525-020-00431-z>
4. Kotler, P., Armstrong, G., Harris, L. C., & Piercy, N. (2021). *Principles of Marketing* (8th European ed.). Pearson.
5. Sigala, M. (2018). New technologies in tourism: From multi-disciplinary to anti-disciplinary advances and trajectories. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 25, 151–155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tmp.2017.12.003>
6. Xiang, Z., & Fesenmaier, D. R. (2017). Big data analytics, tourism design, and smart tourism. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, 6(2), 80–88. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2017.05.003>

Proofreader: Zokir ALIBEKOV
Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2026. № 5

© When materials are reproduced, the INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY journal must be cited as the source. Authors are responsible for the accuracy of the information in materials and advertisements published in the journal. Editorial opinions may not always align with those of the authors. Submitted materials will not be returned to the editorial office.

To publish articles in this journal, you may submit articles, advertisements, stories, and other creative materials through the following links. Materials and advertisements are published on a paid basis.

You may subscribe to the journal at any time using the following details. Once subscribed, please send a screenshot or photo of your payment confirmation to our Telegram page @iqtisodiyot_77. Based on this, we will send the latest issue of the journal to your address each month.

“The journal “INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY” has been registered by the Agency for Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan from 09.10.2024 under the registration number №390637. License number: C-5669633. PNFL: 30407832680027

Our address: Tashkent city, Yunusobod district, 19th block,
House 17.

Acceptance of articles

Published every
monthly

Directions

Social, economic, political,
technological, scientific

Scopus || Scientific electronic journal specializing in Scopus

CERTIFICATE NUMBER: №390637

ORDER NUMBER ACCORDING TO THE LICENSE REGISTER: C-5669633

CONTACT:

Contact us
+998 50 737 87 88

Telegram channel
t.me/scopus_IST2100

Journal official website
<https://ist-journal.uz/index.php/IST>